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Chain Sliding versus β -Sheet Formation upon Shearing Single α -Helical Coiled Coils

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This library contains the circular dichroism (CD) spectra as well as the data from CD thermal denaturation (TD) experiments. It further contains atomic force microscope (AFM)-based single-molecule force spectroscopy (SMFS) data, specifically the selected force-extension curves used for Bell-Evans analysis. The SMFS raw data are published as separate Zenodo entries. Please find additional information also in the supplementary material of the article.

1. CD spectra

CD spectra were collected for all coiled coils (CCs) and the individual CC-forming peptides to obtain information about their secondary structure in native conditions. Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) pH 7.4 was used for all measurements. All data was measured with a Chirascan CD spectrometer, using a quartz cuvette with 1 mm path length (Hellma Analytics). Measurements were performed in a wavelength range from 200 to 250 nm with 1 nm step size. The zipped folder <02_CD_Spectra> is organized into subfolders for the individual peptides and the CCs. The subfolders <Apeptides> and <Bpeptides> contain the data for each respective peptide, measured as one repeat (e.g. A4N3). The subfolder <CC> contains the data for the CCs, measured as three independent repeats (e.g. A4N3B4N3_1-3). All .txt files contain two columns, reporting the wavelength and the CD signal in mdeg.

2. CD thermal denaturation

The thermodynamic stability of the CCs was assessed using thermal denaturation (TD) experiments over a temperature range from 4 to 90 °C in PBS (native) or 1.5 M GuHCl in PBS (GuHCl). In addition, TD experiments were performed for all individual peptides in native conditions. All data was measured with a Chirascan CD spectrometer, using a quartz cuvette with 1 mm path length. The zipped folder <03_CD_ThermalDenaturation> data is organized into subfolders <Apeptides> and <Bpeptides> and <CC>. For each A- or B-peptide, one TD measurement was recorded (e.g. A4N3_TD). For each CC, three independent TD repeats were performed (e.g. A4N3B4N3_TD_1-3 or A4N3B4N3_TD_GuHCl_1-3). The .txt files include the CD signal (in mdeg) for the wavelength range from 200 to 250 nm, at each measured temperature.

The melting temperatures were determined using Global3 analysis software (Applied Photophysics). The resulting melting temperatures can be found in the supplementary material of the article.

3. AFM-based SMFS

The mechanical stability of the CCs was investigated using AFM-SMFS (again using PBS pH 7.4). Measurements were performed at six different retract speeds (50, 200, 400, 1000, 2500 and 5000 nm s⁻¹) to obtain information about the dynamic mechanical range of each CC. Three independent experiments (with different cantilevers and surfaces) were performed for each CC (labelled as CL1 to CL3).

The zipped folders with the numbers 04 to 15 and the name <nr_SMFS_CC_proc_CL> (e.g. 04_SMFS_A4N3B4N3_proc_CL1) contain force-extension curves (processed; proc) that were selected for further analysis. The raw data containing all measured force-extension curves are published as separate datasets.

The data was processed using the JPKSPM data processing software (Version 6.1.41, JPK instruments), applying the following steps:

- post-calibration data of the cantilever were inserted

- baseline correction of the retract part of the curves was performed
- contact point with the surface was defined (correction of x-offset)
- correction for cantilever bending
- force-extension curves displaying single rupture events were fitted with the wormlike chain model

Each zipped folder 04 to 15 contains subfolders for the different retract speeds. These subfolders contain the selected force-extension curves saved in .txt format. The zipped folder 16_SMFS_Chainfits contains the fit results, i.e. the determined rupture forces (column breaking force) and loading rates (column critical loading rate). The data is saved in .tsv format and can be opened with a text editor, e.g. notepad.

A Gaussian fit was used to obtain the most probable values from the distributions of the rupture forces and loading rates. Fits were performed in IgorPro (Version 7.0.8.1, Wavemetrics Inc.). The resulting most probable values (most probable rupture force [pN] and most probable loading rate [pN s⁻¹]) are listed in the supplementary material of the manuscript.